

Report D2.1

“TLO/MLO Workshop Report”

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Report D2.1

“TLO/MLO Workshop Report”

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Task	T2.1 Networking and Consultation
Lead author	Emanuele Ghedini (UNIBO)
Contributors	All WP2 Partners
Peer reviewers	Stefano Borgo
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0.3	25/03/2022	Emanuele Ghedini	Final Version

Glossary of terms

<i>Item</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>TLO</i>	<p>Top Level Ontology.</p> <p>A top-level ontology is an ontology (in the sense used in information science) which consists of very general terms (such as "object", "property", "relation") that are common across all domains.</p>
<i>MLO</i>	<p>Middle Level Ontologies.</p> <p>Mid-level ontologies are primarily intended to extend those concepts towards a specific discipline (e.g., manufacturing, materials science, chemistry) with the aim to provide a core shared vocabulary for lower-level modules. A MLO will provide a higher level of detail than a TLO, extending the taxonomical structure of the ontology more along on the horizontal dimension (i.e., sibling classes under the same superclass).</p>

Keywords

Top Level Ontology, Middle Level Ontology.

Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

The objective of D2.1 is to report on the T2.1 activities on the TLO/MLO multidisciplinary workshop, spanning from the philosophical community to formal TLO/MLO developers and users, to present OntoCommons project, gather existing experience and agreement on OCES methodology and TLOs choice. The details of the workshop organization and attendance, the results of the questionnaire and the final survey document are presented and commented.

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1. Introduction

The objective of D2.1 is to report on the T2.1 activities related to the online TLO/MLO multidisciplinary workshop “*Top-Level and Mid-Level Ontologies Multi-Disciplinary Workshop*” that took place in **three afternoon sessions** from 14:00 to 18:30 on the 25th of March, 29th of March and 8th of April 2021, and with a **final consensus meeting** on the 24th of May with the workshop invited speakers as representatives for the community.

The workshop target audience spanned from the philosophical community to formal TLO/MLO developers and users, as required in the DoA, to ensure a truly multi-disciplinary approach. The purpose was to present OntoCommons project, gather existing experience and agreement on OCES methodology and TLOs choice.

The TLO/MLO workshop scope was to **identify and collect input from existing stakeholders** and search for further resources through a **relevant stakeholder engagement activity**. At the same time, as requested in the DoA, there was the need to present the set of initial TLOs (i.e., BFO, DOLCE and EMMO) and collect an **agreement on the methodology**, together with suggestion for the further extension of TRO towards other TLOs.

The **huge participation (>200 registered participants)** to this event, and the proactive attitude of the communities to discuss and provide feedback are an indication of an effective engagement of stakeholders and project openness.

This document will summarize the organisational steps, in terms of content and speaker definitions (Section 2), the workshop content and participant profiles (Section Workshop3), the survey results (Section 0), the consensus meeting (Section 5) and some final conclusions (Section 0)

2. Organization

2.1 Organizers

The organization of the workshop took place as joint initiative in which all members of WP2 provided contributions in terms of specific expertise on the topic subject of the workshop to define its contents and methodologies. An important contribution, that led to a wide engagement of communities, came from the strong connections of OntoCommons partners with several important stakeholders in the TLO community. It is noteworthy to mention CNR (already a strong reference point for the ontological community) and ENIT (through the Industrial Ontology Foundry network) as pivotal partners in terms of networking connections with TLO communities.

UNIBO as task leader, led the organisation and practical workshop management activities, together with the support of WP6 for website, registration, and survey management. The European Materials Modelling Council (EMMC) provided the AirMeet platform for hosting the event.

Figure 1 - TLO/MLO Workshop Banner

2.2 Methodology

The methodology to reach stakeholders, present OntoCommons, get feedback and gather agreement has been widely discussed within WP2 in the first months of the project. The workshop has been designed from the beginning to **attract stakeholders** proposing an **opportunity for TLO/MLO and Experts to show the status of their activities** to an **audience interested into exploiting ontologies in their domain of interest**. Such gathering has been functional to the presentation of OntoCommons to a qualified audience (researchers, developers, and users) and ask for further commitments.

The non-technical organizational steps, relevant for the scope of the workshop of the have been:

- **Pre-workshop:**
 - o Definition of the main stakeholder categories: TLO, MLO and TOOL (experts about ontology usage and tools development)
 - o Identification of the relevant stakeholders for each of the TLO, MLO and Experts categories
 - o Contact and engage relevant stakeholders as speakers for the workshop
 - o Agenda definition
 - o Webpage publication and invitation to general (non-speaker) stakeholders
 - o Survey definition and publication
- **Intra-workshop**
 - o Survey analysis and presentation
- **Post-workshop**
 - o Building a consensus document
 - o Define possible TLO for OntoCommons TRO further extension

2.3 Content Definition and Speakers Selection

The contents of TLO, MLO and TOOLS topics to be addressed during the workshop by a dedicated speaker have been defined using WP1 first analysis of the existing stakeholders, together with the WP2 partners experience¹. Figure 1 summarizes the TLO and MLO initiatives, the contacts name and affiliation, and the proponent partners in charge of engaging him. Few other initiatives have been contacted without success (e.g., OntoCape, SUMO). The speakers list length has been defined to keep the workshop in the limits of three half-days, while at the same time provide enough time for each speaker to sufficiently present his initiative.

	TLO/MLO NAME	NAME	AFFILIATION	EMAIL	PROPONENT
TLO	BFO	Barry Smith	University of Buffalo	phismith@buffalo.edu	OntoCommons
	EMMO	Emanuele Ghedini	University of Bologna	emanuele.ghedini@unibo.it	OntoCommons
	DOLCE	Stefano Borgo	CNR	stefano.borgo@cnr.it	OntoCommons
	GFO	Heinrich Herre	Leipzig University	heinrich.herre@imise.uni-leipzig.de	CNR
	UFO	Giancarlo Guizzardi	Free University of Bozen	giancarlo.guizzardi@unibz.it	CNR
	ISO 15926	Matthew West	Information Junction Ltd	dr.matthew.west@gmail.com	GCL
	Tupper-PSL	Michael Gruninger	University of Toronto	gruninger@mie.utoronto.ca	CNR
	YAMATO	Riichiro Mizoguchi	Osaka University	mizo@jaist.ac.jp	CNR
OPM	Dov Dori	Israel Institute of Technology	dori@technion.ac.il	UNIBO	
MLO	BORO/FDM	Chris Partridge	BORO Solutions Limited	partridgec@borogroup.co.uk	GCL
	EMMO MLO	Jesper Friis	SINTEF	jesper.friis@sintef.no	UNIBO
	CCO	Ron Rudnicki	CUBIRC	rudnicki@cubrc.org	ENIT
	AFO	Heiner Oberkamp	Osthus	heiner.oberkamp@osthus.com	GCL
	IOF Core Ontology	Chris Will	IOF	chris.will@outlook.com	ENIT
	The Ontology of Time and Process	Antony Galton	University of Exeter	aggalton@ex.ac.uk	CNR
	ISO/TC 184/SC 4 "Industrial data"	Nils Sandmark		nils.sandmark@posccaesar.org	ENIT
Ontology Design Pattern	Aldo Gangemi	University of Bologna	aldo.gangemi@unibo.it	CNR	
TOOLS	-	Claudio Calosi	University of Geneva	claudio.calosi@unige.ch	UNIBO
	-	Adham Hashibon	Materially	adham.hashibon@materially.tech	UNIBO
	-	Till Mossakowski	University of Magdeburg	till.mossakowski@ovgu.de	CNR
	-	Cassia Trojan	University of Toulouse	Cassia.Trojan@irit.fr	ENIT
-	Pascal Hitzler	Kansas State University	phitzler@googlemail.com / hitzler@k-state.edu	ENIT	

Figure 2 - Speaker Selection

2.4 Invitations

Invitations letters have been drafted to ensure that the expectations and contributions to the workshop were in line with the OntoCommons objectives, informing the stakeholders about the projects scope.

2.4.1 Speakers Invitation

A key for the achievement of the workshop objectives was to make speakers aware of the scope of the workshop and the objectives of the OntoCommons project, especially underlining the pluralistic approach embraced by the project. In fact, speakers were intended to be the most probable stakeholders willing to join the OntoCommons initiatives. To achieve that, a detailed invitation letter has been prepared to instruct speakers, as shown in Figure 3.

2.4.2 Participants Invitation

The most important motivations for non-speaker attendance were supposed to be the opportunity:

1. For TLO/MLO ontologist to be part of a newly creating community

¹ A recent [TLO survey](#) made by the [Digital Twin Hub](#) has been also considered.

2. For DLO/ALO ontologist to understand better how to link with a TLO/MLO ontology
3. For a non-informed attendee to gather information about how to use ontologies in their domain of interest

These motivations have been formalized in the webpage invitation page, shown in Figure 4.

The screenshot shows an email invitation from OntoCommons. It includes the OntoCommons logo, the website URL www.ontocommons.eu, and a letter addressed to a 'Dear Expert'. The letter thanks the expert for accepting an invitation to speak at a workshop on March 25th, 29th, and April 8th. It describes the H2020 CSA project's goal of standardizing data documentation and the development of the Ontology Commons EcoSystem (OCES). It details the workshop's purpose of creating an EU-based network and lists the topics to be discussed, such as linking and comparing approaches. It also specifies the time allocated for speakers (25 minutes for TLO, 20 minutes for MLO and TOOLS) and provides contact information for the WP Leader, Emanuele Ghedini, at the University of Bologna.

 ONTOLOGY-DRIVEN
DATA DOCUMENTATION
FOR INDUSTRY COMMONS

www.ontocommons.eu

Dear Expert,

on the behalf of the **H2020 OntoCommons** project we would like to thank you for accepting the invitation to be a speaker at the **Top Level and Mid Level Ontologies Multidisciplinary Workshop** that will be held online in three separate sessions on Thursday 25th March, Monday 29th March, and Thursday 8th April, from 14:00 to 18:00 (CET).

The [OntoCommons](#) project is an **H2020 CSA project** dedicated to the standardisation of data documentation across all domains related to materials and manufacturing. OntoCommons lays the foundations for interoperable, harmonised and standardised data documentation through ontologies, facilitating data sharing and pushing data-driven innovation, to bring out a truly Digital Single Market and new business models for European industry, exploit the opportunities of digitalisation and address sustainability challenges.

The project addresses its goal by developing the **Ontology Commons EcoSystem (OCES)** - a set of ontologies and tools that follows specific standardisation rules - and provide a sustainable approach, making the data FAIR.

The **workshop** is primarily intended to gather Top Level Ontology (TLO) and Mid Level Ontology (MLO) stakeholders to create a EU-based network, spanning from the philosophical community to formal TLO/MLO developers and users. During the workshop, we will present the OntoCommons project structure and objectives. Speakers and attendees will be given the opportunity to contribute to the definition of the challenges and requirements of the Ontology EcoSystem and to be involved in its development activities.

You will be requested to shortly report about the **main choices behind your work** and your **ideas about linking/comparing it with other approaches**, under a **pluralistic framework**. You will be allocated a slot of **25 minutes for TLO** speakers and **20 minutes for MLO and TOOLS** speakers, including short clarification questions.

Please, note that we do not expect a full presentation nor a sale pitch, but rather an attempt to let us understand your position in the ontology landscape and pave the way for a fruitful collaboration in the framework of the H2020 OntoCommons initiative on ontology based data documentation.

The agenda of the event can be found as attachment.

Best regards,

The OntoCommons WP2 *Top Reference Ontology* Team

WP Leader and contact:
Emanuele Ghedini
University of Bologna
emanuele.ghedini@unibo.it

Figure 3 - Speaker Invitation Letter

www.ontocommons.eu

Top-Level and Mid-Level Ontologies Multi-Disciplinary Workshop

Collaborative Workshop

A pluralistic approach for the highest ontological levels

25 March - 29 March - 8 April 2021, 14:00 - 18:00 CET

The **Top-Level and Mid-Level Ontologies Multi-Disciplinary Workshop** is primarily intended to gather Top Level Ontology (TLO) and Mid-Level Ontology (MLO) stakeholders to create an EU based network, spanning from the philosophical community to formal TLO/MLO developers and users.

During the workshop we will ask some of the most relevant TLO and MLO developers and users to **present their actual progress** in the field, to **depict the status and the role of high-level ontologies** in the strategic perspective of **European Industry digitalisation**.

The workshop will give the opportunity to all attendees to contribute to the OntoCommons goal to create a **Top Reference Ontology** to facilitate alignments and comparisons between TLOs and MLOs, which will constitute the core of the OntoCommons EcoSystem (OCES): a set of ontologies and tools in the industrial domain following state-of-the-art FAIR rules that will enable end users to harvest their potential at different levels, according to their specific needs.

Participant will take active role in the discussion, both during and after the event, providing valuable feedback to the OntoCommons project in the form of community driven objectives and strategic priorities, together with the identification of the bottlenecks that prevents further use of ontologies in the EU and the opportunities not yet fully exploited.

Participant are asked to register to the OntoCommons website and fill the dedicated questionnaire. A confirmation email will be sent by the organizers.

Who should join?

Top Level and Mid-Level ontology developers that want to:

- **participate** to the EU coordinated initiative for ontology-based Data Documentation
- **connect** with other relevant stakeholders in the ontology fields
- **find opportunities** for the exploitation of their ontology development

Ontology users that want to:

- **understand** the opportunities that adopting a TLO/MLO may provide
- **contribute** to a strategy for developing new framework and tools to improve their experience with ontologies
- **stay up-to-date** with respect to the most recent developments
- **formalize their knowledge** into an ontological framework for data documentation and interoperability
- **introduce** themselves into the field of ontologies

Industrial Stakeholders that want to:

- **understand** the opportunities that adopting a TLO/MLO may provide
- **stay updated** with the EU initiatives in the field of data digitalisation
- **contribute** to include the needs of industry in the field of high level ontologies

Figure 4 - Website General Invitation Letter

2.5 Agenda

The agenda of the event is shown in Figure 5. The first day was also devoted to the OntoCommons introduction delivered by Coordinators and WP2 leader, together with a talk from Anne de Baas as former EC Officer and organizers of past ontology-based events in Brussels within the EC.

A lecture on the first day from Stefano Borgo (CNR) was intended to introduce the topic of top-level ontologies, while the lecture of the philosopher of science Claudio Calosi (University of Geneva) was intended to provide a more philosophical direct perspective about ontologies for physics. The half day structure was intended to make the workshop easier to fit in the existing agendas, and the afternoon placement to facilitate the attendance from the USA.

Top-Level and Mid-Level Ontologies Multi-Disciplinary Workshop			
AGENDA			
CET			
DAY 1			25 March 2021
14:00	5	Introduction	Welcome
14:05	15		Nadja Adamovic (TUWIEN)
14:20	5		OntoCommons Project Presentation and Objectives
14:25	15		Hedi Karay (ENIT)
14:40	15		Workshop Structure and Scope
			Emanuele Ghedini (UNIBO)
			OntoCommons: a Top Reference Ontology for TLOs/MLOs alignment
			Emanuele Ghedini (UNIBO)
			Ontologies and Interoperability in the NMBP Domain
			Anne de Baas
14:55	25	Lecture	What are and what role for TLOs?
			Stefano Borgo (CNR)
15:20	15	Break	
15:35	25	TLOs	GFO
16:00	25		Heinrich Herre
16:25	25		Tupper-PSL
16:50	25		Michael Gruninger
17:15	25		UFO
			Giancarlo Guizzardi
			YAMATO
			Richiro Mizoguchi
			OPM
			Dov Dori
17:40	20	MLOs	The Ontology of Time and Process
			Antony Galton
18:00		Conclusions Day 1	
CEST			
DAY 2			29 March 2021
14:00	25	Lecture	Ontologies and Philosophy of Science
			Claudio Calosi
14:25	25	TLOs	BFO
14:50	25		Barry Smith
15:15	25		DOLCE
15:40	25		Claudio Masolo
16:05	25		EMMO
			Emanuele Ghedini
			BORO
			Chris Partridge
			ISO15926
			Matthew West
16:30	15	Break	
16:45	20	MLOs	EMMO MLO
17:05	20		Jesper Friis
17:25	20		Common Core Ontologies
17:45	20		Ron Rudnicki
18:05	20	AFO	
			Heiner Oberkamp
			IOF Core Ontology
			Chris Will
18:25		TLOs	SIO
			Michel Dumontier
18:25		Conclusions Day 2	
CEST			
DAY 3			8 April 2021
14:00	20	EXPERTS	HETS
14:20	20		Till Mossakowski
14:40	20		Matching top and domain ontologies
15:00	20		Cassia Trojan
15:20	20		Ontology Design Patterns
15:40	20		Aldo Gangemi
			Digital Marketplaces/Simulation Platforms
			Adham Hashibon
			ISO/TC 184/SC 4 "Industrial data"
			Nils Sandmark
			The Upper Ontology Alignment Tool
			Pascal Hitzler
16:00	15	Break	
16:15	15	Future Events	
16:30	45	Survey Results and Discussion	
17:15	45	OntoTrans Project Feedback	
18:00		End Of Workshop	

Figure 5 - Workshop Agenda

3. Workshop

3.1 Attendance

There were 207 workshop registered participants (see Appendix 7.2) for the overall workshop. A brief analysis of the participation by country is done in Figure 6, showing a predominant European interest from Germany and Italy, followed by UK and Norway. From the American area, a strong representative of Brazilian participants is observed, followed by a lesser participation from the USA.

Looking at the participation by professional status, as shown in Figure 7, we observe a predominant participation by researchers in general, compared to pure ontologists, that underlines the relevant interest that stands behind the applications of ontologies, followed by scientists and engineers. Declared ontologists were only the 10% of the attendees.

The attendance through the three days' workshop is as follows, according to Airmeet report in terms of significative presence of the attendee:

25th March

- Introduction: 93
- Top-Level Ontologies Part I: 91

29th March

- Top-Level Ontologies Part II: 101
- Mid-Level Ontologies: 70

8th April

- Tools and Applications: 78

3.2 Presentations

The presentations made explicitly publicly available by the speakers have been collected and attached as attachment to this deliverable.

Figure 6 - Participants by Country

Figure 7 - Participants by Profession

4. Questionnaire

4.1 Scope

The questionnaire was aimed to collect preliminary information to help organizers to address the topic that will be discussed during the workshop and to prepare the final workshop report. The complete text of the survey is available in the Appendix 7.1. The complete (anonymous) survey result is available as attachment to this deliverable. A total of 40 complete questionnaire have been collected.

4.2 Survey Results

The results of the questionnaire have been thoroughly analysed and presented during the third workshop day. In the following figure it is possible to check the average numerical value (from 0 to 10) assigned by each attendee to the sentences suggested in the questionnaire, together with the standard deviation.

Workshop Scope II

An ontology should always refer to a Top Level Ontology.

6.69/10 (σ 2.81)

A top level ontology can **improve the quality of an ontology**, however **it may not be necessary** if the ontology is a lightweight ontology or something simple like a taxonomy.

In principle I would say yes. But there **might be cases where it is not needed**, like some small self-sufficient application that used an ontology for internal purposes.

An ontology can refer to a TLO at a **later time**.

Important but **not always possible**

To reuse and integrate ontologies, **it is crucial that they start from the same conceptual basis**. If the ontologies disagree in the most abstract aspects, the remaining classes will propagate this disagreement.

Always is too strong a word. It depends on the application for which the ontology is intended.

The top ontology provides the ontological content, **without it there is no ontological content**.

Workshop Scope II

A TLO greatly facilitates the development of ontologies in general.

7.58/10 (σ 2.02)

Provides a starting point with **major philosophical issues already considered**

Again if you **work in your corner** you can "easily" develop your own ontology. The TLO **helps bridge to other ontologies** but the structuring/organisation can also be achieved "locally".

Yes, it greatly helps with **consistency** and providing a **theoretical sound basis** (given that the TLO is theoretically sound).

As long as it doesn't add to **much overhead** it gives good guidance and clearer shared conceptualization.

Skilled modelers are scarce...

I think they are **essential for interoperability**.

It helps, but it usually is **not easy to connect to some TLO**

If you wish to develop an ontology under the umbrella of a specific TLO it will definitely **greatly facilitate the development**. However, if you wish to develop an ontology in general, it **might inhibit development**, if one wants to cater to several TLOs.

Workshop Scope II

TLOs are difficult to understand since they refer to terms and concepts not clearly understandable by people working on the application fields.

6.42/10 (σ 2.35)

For example, **occurrent is not a common term that is easy to understand by non specialist;**

In my limited experience so far it can be difficult to **categorise domain-specific terms** (e.g. is a system an object or collection of objects?)

It is up to the TLO-builders to **explain** what the meaning is. This being said it is **not always easy to dig up from the manual of an ontology what philosophical commitments** are used as a base.

You have to **spend some time to understand a TLO** in order to be able to use it correctly. Using **TLOs may be a barrier for some people**, but can also help you creating a more consistent ontology.

Domain experts seldom grasp TLO

This is true, unfortunately, and in many cases **the reason why they are not used**.

Yes, it's **relatively difficult** for somebody without an a good ontology knowledge to understand a TLO straight away

True. The **MLOs are more understandable than TLOs**.

Workshop Scope II

A clear philosophical commitment (e.g. realism, nominalism) is important for a TLO.

6.42/10 (σ 2.83)

Yes, TLOs should be philosophically and theoretically **consistent**.

It affects the domain on the one-hand. On the other-hand, **domain experts might not care**.

I would agree that it is "important" in that it should be considered, but **I don't know if it is actually necessary**, and overemphasis of the philosophical aspects **may even get in the way of created a "practical and usable" ontology**

A philosophical commitment is particularly **critical to modeling abstract entities**.

In case of application, they are **not that important**.

Depends on what you mean by philosophy. There are metaphysical ones like BFO written by philosophers and reflecting their view, and there are others that are more aligned with mathematics and logic. Some look to be inspired by physics or engineering.

I do not understand the question.

04/11/2021

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 | 10.

Workshop Scope II

There is not a single TLO which is valid for all purposes, since there are more ways to express general concepts depending on the ontologist perspective.

7.39/10 (σ 2.58)

Each existing ontology has made commitments, but **it seems to be possible to make a meta-ontology that encompasses all of these**.

Since there are many TLO, with conflicting commitments, there **isn't a one-size fits all approach**

From my experience, although a single "ontology" might be a philosophical ideal, it is almost **certainly not a practical reality**.

I am a little bit ambivalent on this one. I think, at least in **science, it should be possible to have one TLO** to be valid for all research purposes. However, I also think that this **TLO will not be optimal for all research purposes**.

Committing to a **single TLO for science is a trade-off between efficiency and interoperability**, I guess.

I think **the use of different TLOs is a reality that cannot be neglected**. Maybe an ideal world everyone could agree on a single TLO, but currently, **we are not there**.

There is **always a single TLO** considering the standard language

Yes. Perspective matters.

04/11/2021

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 | 11.

Workshop Scope II

I prefer to stick on the conceptualization/axiomatization developed ad hoc for my approach than changing my perspective adopting a more general TLO/MLO.

3.61/10 (σ 2.88)

Disagree pretty strongly. I think TLOs and MLOs are **definitely useful**. And I like that there are many to choose from so that one can pick the TLO/MLO that aligns with the perspective of domain experts.

I would like very much **to get a TLO which can be used in many disciplines**, particularly for **engineering applications**.

Depends on the level / granularity / genericity of my ontology

Past investments will make people answer yes, but as **the world is merging people will have to link in to other domains and thus need a bridge**.

My attempts so far lead me to believe that **TLOs have already answered some of the higher-level philosophical questions**, and so following this framework is actually easier than an ad hoc approach

Workshop Scope II

Adoption of common TLO/MLO greatly enhances interoperability between ontologies.

8.61/10 (σ 2.07)

If domain ontologies use TLOs they can be **linked or integrated easier** since they share common underlying concepts

Obviously, of using common repeatable patterns at the application ontology level, gives no such **guarantees** and no means to review or validate for such consistency.

I didn't choose 10 because **there might be some TLOs that are so opaque as to even inhibit interoperability**.

Sure, but is it **possible** ?

It's early days to say conclusively, **but I definitely lean toward agreement**.

Workshop Scope II

In the trade off between expressivity (e.g. FOL vs RDF) and tractability (e.g. undecidability vs decidability, computational efficiency) I prefer tractability.

4.75/10 (σ 2.62)

I understand the trade-off and understand applications need tractability. But I think that **we should strengthen "reasoning generating new knowledge"** as that might **temper the politically-induced AI -hype**.

Expressivity is more important

Expressivity (conceptual models) and computational efficiency (implementational models) are **both important** and necessary. We should find a **good balance** between them.

I think **both tractability and expressivity are needed**. Hence, I prefer a **heterogeneous approach**, where domain ontologies are mostly written in OWL, with some FOL parts, while for TLOs, it is more the other way round.

No. I believe that we can **too advance in the development of ontologies that value expressiveness**.

In the end, from the Informatics point of view, **what we need is a computational artifact**.

Well, I use computers a lot, **so tractability please**.

Workshop Scope II

The ability to infer new statements from given knowledge is the most important feature for a TLO/MLO.

5.53/10 (σ 2.34)

No, enhanced interoperability is the most important feature of a TLO/MLO. But the ability to infer new knowledge is also important.

It's a useful feature but **not the most important** in any business setting that I have seen so far. That is integration costs, common language requirements to overcome data silos etc. In finance, a lot of effort has been expended under the above assumption and so far, no-one is asking for it. If they aren't, who is?

This is what I consider to be the main benefit of using "ontologies".

Reasoning is **not always required**.

Definitely a **plus for some areas. For others, not so much**.

Workshop Scope II

A good documentation is paramount for the effective use of a TLO/MLO as a basis for DLO.

8.78/10 (σ 2.21)

Couldn't agree more.

Which documentation is meant here?

Yes, but is it possible ?

Yes, and examples

We use BFO, and some our domain experts often have consulted the BFO book. **Without the BFO book, it would have been way more difficult to bring domain experts to use a TLO.**

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 | 16.

Workshop Scope II

A MLO should be defined according to the discipline of interest (e.g. chemistry) instead of according to its formal structure (e.g. taxonomy class levels).

6.64/10 (σ 2.27)

The world is compartmentalised and each domain has already created its ontology. This means there are large overlaps. **To throw all of this out and start afresh encapsulated in one ontology is well not realistic.**

Depends. Both needs are valid.

This is a good point. We are always dealing with **already established domain-specific classificatory systems**. My experience is that in order for users to adopt an ontology it is very important that it at least reuses already established terms (directly or as synonyms). Again, I tend to take a pragmatic approach...

I think **both discipline of interest and formal structure need to be reconciliated somehow.**

Straddling the fence on that one. **Believe in the power of abstractions to bridge disciplines.** Also believe that **some disciplines are hard to define formally.**

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 | 17.

Workshop Scope II

The choice of an ontology for my application is driven by the requirements/limitations of the tools I'm planning to use or that are available to me.

4.92/10 (σ 3.10)

Not so much. If I need an ontology, I'll go to some amount of trouble to use it rather than creating folk art.

In many cases yes. Efforts on my area of applications (I have limited experience) are usually bottom-up, starting from specific information from solvers (software tools)

Of, course, I am center in application

No, the choice is driven by my needs and the use I plan for the ontology

It is driven by the **features required for a system**

I am theory driven and have **no application in mind.**

Workshop Scope II

Quantify the relevance of each of the following ontology levels in practical applications:

- **Top Level Ontologies** 2.31/4 (σ 1.37)
- **Mid Level Ontologies** 2.61/4 (σ 1.06)
- **Domain Level Ontologies** 3.44/4 (σ 0.72)
- **App Level Ontologies** 3.50/4 (σ 0.65)

Most of the _practical_ applications I've seen are **glorified databases**, which **do not benefit directly from a TLO.**

I do not know the concept of mlo, and tlo have **few practical application**

The domain has to be right if you want to solve problems in a given domain. Mid-level ontologies buy some amount of generality that can be useful in **fostering resilience to changing requirements** in an application or methodology. Top ontologies in support of MLOs make **logical sense**, but only if they fit mid-level abstractions well. It's why I approve of the current plurality in TLOs.

Workshop Scope II

There is lack of tools or need for further developments in order to enable or facilitate the TLO/MLO development and usage in practice:

- **Editors** 2.97/4 (σ 1.01)
- **Reasoners** 2.69/4 (σ 0.99)
- **Provers** 2.53/4 (σ 1.14)
- **Visualization** 3.06/4 (σ 1.03)
- **Optimization** 2.94/4 (σ 0.94)

Can't author without a good editor. Can't see what you did without visualization. Provers and optimizers are higher-level tools that could be very useful **depending on the circumstances**.

There is a **great lack of an efficient and high-quality FOSS reasoner** with a developer community around that can be used and integrated into open source projects.

All the characteristics are important.

In my opinion, editors and visualization are the most important characteristics to build and use an ontology.

Workshop Scope II

What are the bottlenecks or unresolved issues that are actually preventing or slowing the use of ontologies in Europe scientific and industrial landscape?

Tools

Too many competing TLOs, which one to use? Too many silos at domain-level, not often willing to share or make interoperable

The **battles between owners of different ontologies** seem to hamper progress and adoption. These owners should acknowledge the need to harmonise and realise this does not mean they "loose" or "become invisible". A harmonised ecosystem will create trust in industry. Standardisation should not be the first goal but should grow over time.

A main bottleneck is **competence**. There is a lack of people that are able to write good and reusable ontologies.

Lack of good tooling and eco-systems that makes it easy and efficient to map existing data sources to ontological concepts is greatly slowing down the development.

Lack of interoperability

Clear communication, which problem classes can be solved with ontologies and even more, which problems can't be solved with ontologies. **Education and training**. **Incentives** for using ontologies in the scientific community.

To demonstrate and prove that ontologies allow us to **build a better information system** and will help in the decision make process.

I think there is **not enough knowledge on how to develop and use ontologies in the field**, in industry.

In industry, particularly in the engineering area, there is almost **no information about the possibility to use ontologies**. EMMC is starting to provide a good path on materials, but it is on a very limited area.

Workshop Scope II

What are the unexploited capabilities of ontologies that could contribute to the digitalisation of scientific and industrial sectors?

Data documentation

My motivation for using ontologies is to **enable computers to more accurately match knowledge "needs" and "seeds"** (finding the "diamond in the rough"). The goal is to match a knowledge seeker with a knowledge provider that the seeker does not know but should know. To do this, we need descriptors for human knowledge that are "understandable" by computers. I believe that logical reasoning based on DL Ontologies (with support from rules) is the most effective way to approach this.

Linking data from various sources

Expression of well established technical standards (ISO, DIN, BS, ...) as ontologies and linked data.

In many areas, ontologies could help with **standardisation of terminology**, with data integration etc. management / representation / classification of **big data**

Using the ontology graph to do implement **workflow reasoning, ML/AI deductions and autonomy**.

I think **model-based development is unfortunately rare in application and system development**. My interest there is what led me to ontologies. The appeal of model-based development is that it leads to designs and implementation that are well aligned with the domain in which reasoning and software are applied. And that makes them more resilient to change.

4.3 Attendee Profile

To facilitate the understanding of the questionnaire result by the audience, a monologue has been created by putting together all the results and relevant answers to the questionnaire topics, to depict an ideal average attendee profile:

"I **would** really like for **every ontology to refer to a TLO**, since they for sure facilitate the development of specific ontologies and **greatly enhance interoperability**. However, TLO are sometimes **not clearly understandable by non-expert** people working on the application field, that are only **partially interested on the philosophical commitment** of the TLO, if it works for them. By the way, it's almost an **absolute truth that a good documentation** is the priority for a TLO!

It is also quite evident that there **is not a single TLO valid for each application domain**, that's why I'm looking forward to having some **bridging between ontologies**. Also **reusing work done within existing disciplines** should be the way for **MLO** definition and development, instead of starting from scratch from the top.

I know there is a trade-off between **expressivity and tractability**, but it should be solved **depending on the application case**, with TLOs providing **scalable expressivity versions to be chosen by the users**. The same holds for **reasoning, that may be useful to in the AI field but generally not always used**. From an application perspective, the **tools** often impose constraints to the choice of ontology expressivity, but this may not be the case for a theoretical ontologist.

I feel a **lack of tools**, especially **editors, visualizers, and optimizers**, and of **competences in the education** of potential users, scientific communities, and industry. Another bottleneck is the

competition between TLO that may create **ontological silos** that jeopardize the overall TLOs efforts, and that can be overcome by clear communication and documentation.”

5. Consensus Meeting

5.1 Participants

The consensus meeting following the elaboration of workshop results has been held by UNIBO Teams platform on the 24th of May 2021. A total of 19 attendees were present, including WP2 partners and workshop speakers:

Emanuele Ghedini
Anne de Baas
Guizzardi Giancarlo
Matthew West
Jesper Friis
Chris Partridge
Stefano Borgo
Hedi Karray
Claudio Masolo
Gerhard Goldbeck
Adham Hashibon
Arkopaul Sarkar
Dimitrios Kyritsis
Dov Dori
Nils Sandsmark
Emilio Sanfilippo
Riichiro Mizoguchi
Michael Gruninger
Aldo Gangemi

5.2 Summary Document

The meeting defined a set of sentences summarizing the workshop outcomes here.

Workshop Outcome Summary and Proposed Strategies

1. **Referring to a common TLO within an organization, community or project** or a framework of mapped TLOs for the development of a domain specific ontology (MLO, DLO or ALO) **facilitates its development** and **greatly enhances interoperability** between ontologies.

TLOs² should provide a sound theoretical foundation of consistent and well-defined logical theories and interpretation frameworks that should fit the needs of large communities of users, saving the time and cost for the from scratch development and the requirements of specific skills (e.g., conceptual and ontology engineering, logics) that are not actually be available within each specific community.

However, the overhead of introducing a TLO may not be justified in all application cases (e.g., small projects) and partial or no TLO adoption could be the fastest and cheapest approach. We suggest that initiatives with a large scope and ambition funded by public institutions (such as Horizon Europe initiatives, or European national initiatives) or large companies, should adopt an organization wide TLO approach and a TLO based framework like the one proposed by OntoCommons. In this sense, demonstrators may play an important role in showing the capabilities and limits of TLO.

2. There is a **disciplinary barrier** towards the adoption of TLOs, since they refer to **terms and concepts coming from the ontology or philosophy vocabulary** that are **often obscure to people working in a specific application field**. Therefore, the TLO terms and concepts should be accessible and understandable to users.

TLOs can be a barrier for some people since domain experts seldom grasp TLOs approach and architecture, and in many cases is the reason why they are not used. MLO and DLO are easier to understand by non-ontology experts that usually refer directly to them.

² TLO = Top Level Ontology, MLO = Mid-Level Ontology, DLO = Domain Level Ontology, ALO = Application-Level Ontology

A well-defined and accurate adoption route (e.g., dedicated training courses and educational paths), together with good documentation should be the priority for a TLO to overcome some of these barriers.

3. There may be multiple TLOs suitable to represent any application. For this reason, **it is not expected, nor is reasonably feasible to assume that a single specific TLO will be chosen by all the communities**. A bridging between TLOs seems possible and is needed to retain a community preferred approach and at the same time provide ways to share knowledge with other communities.

There are many TLOs, expressions of different communities, often with conflicting commitments, so that there isn't a one-size fits all approach. A single ontology might be a philosophical ideal, but it is almost certainly not a practical reality and the use of many different TLOs in practice is a reality that cannot be neglected, nor removed. There should be a trade-off between a generic TLOs pluralism and the focus on single approaches to be found within each specific area of interest.

A scalable approach to alignment between different ontologies (from syntactical to terminological and finally conceptual, depending on the specific application case), is the suggested route to deal with such *de facto* pluralism, as proposed by OntoCommons.

4. There is a strong difference in the approaches and objectives **while going from pure ontologists to application domain users**.
 - a. Languages: ontologies need to exist in different representations that address different (and sometimes incompatible) requirements. Amongst the objectives, some of these representations will optimize expressivity (which are important to some communities and applications), others will optimize computational performance.
 - b. Tractability...
 - c. Epistemological ambition...

TLO authors are often focused on expressivity, philosophical commitments, and generality of the approach, while application domain experts focus on "getting the things done". Expressivity (conceptual models) and computational efficiency (implementational models) are both important and necessary. We should find a good balance between them since there is still space to advance in the development of ontologies that value expressiveness.

Both tractability and expressivity are needed: a heterogeneous approach, where the same ontology can be provided at different levels of expressivity (e.g., from HOL to XML and RDBs) is advisable. There is a trade-off between expressivity and tractability, but it should be solved depending on

the application case, with TLOs providing scalable expressivity versions to be chosen by the users. The same holds for reasoning, that may be useful in the AI field but generally not always used.

5. We need professional tools for Ontology Engineering. Tools that leverage on and that are aligned with TLOs. These include tools for validation (not only verification), code generators, complexity management tools, as well as tools that help with ontology reuse, including leveraging on ontology patterns and anti-patterns

Limited existing tools often impose constraints to the choice of ontology expressivity. However, the tractability needed by the applications may be reached by strengthening symbolic based reasoning, also to be proposed as an alternative to current AI approaches.

We should push for actions to raise the awareness about the need of tools for ontology development. Lack of good tooling and ecosystems that makes it easy and efficient to map existing data sources to ontological concepts is greatly slowing down the development.

6. There is a **lack of multi-disciplinary competences** within all the communities involved in ontology development and usage.

Potential users, scientific communities and industry are often affected by a competence bottleneck. There is a lack of people that can write good and reusable ontologies.

Clear communication, which problem classes can be solved with ontologies and even more, which problems can't be solved with ontologies. We need education and training, together with incentives for using ontologies in the scientific community and in industry.

7. Clear communication based on understanding of common principles, differences, and capabilities between TLOs communities, as well as concrete mappings, should be developed to prevent creating **ontological silos** that could jeopardize the overall TLOs efforts.

Tightening the TLO community providing a common discussion ground and the effort to understand similarities and differences can be the way to overcome this bottleneck. TLO communities should work together to strengthen their overall position towards policy makers. The OntoCommons initiative is an opportunity to achieve that.

8. MLO definition faces the challenges of **being coherent with the existing definitions or standards** provided by each discipline of interest (e.g., chemistry, metrology), and at the same time **to provide constraints on the formal structure of the ontological representation of the discipline** (e.g., taxonomy class levels). A clear separation between disciplines is not a realistic goal since each domain has already created its standard terminology and definitions.

We are always dealing with already established domain-specific classificatory systems that often lack rigorous and consistent logical structure and introduce ambiguities in the definitions. It is very important that a MLO at least reuses already established terms and standards, instead of starting from scratch from the top, using a pragmatic approach in which we propose changes also to already established standards, to improve their consistency in an ontological environment. It is reasonable to believe that abstractions can help bridging disciplines, even if some disciplines are very hard to be formally defined.

5.3 TLOs Agreement

Besides the pre-defined OntoCommons ontologies, already listed in the DoA:

- **BFO**, Contact: Barry Smith
- **DOLCE**, Contact: Nicola Guarino
- **EMMO**, Contact: Emanuele Ghedini

there has been an expression interest in joining OntoCommons activities by:

- **UFO**, Contact: Giancarlo Guizzardi
- **OPM ISO19450**, Contact: Dov Dori
- **TUPPER**, Contact: Michel Gruninger
- (**GFO**, Contact: Heinrich Herre)
- (**YAMATO**, Contact: Riichiro Mizoguchi)
- (**ISO15926**, Contact: Matthew West)

WP2 development actions will propose periodical meetings open to non OntoCommons members to involve such communities during the T2.4 and T2.5 activities.

6. Conclusions

The TLO/MLO ontology workshop addressed the objectives of:

- **gather stakeholders** embracing a **multidisciplinary** audience including philosophers, scientists, engineers, software developers, and ontologists
- **collect experiences** in the field of TLO/MLO and applications that can be used to build a strategy and define a methodology to achieve the project results
- gather an **agreement on more TLOs** to be included in the TRO

The results of the workshop, as summarized in the previous sections, depict a **very large ontology community** that focuses on the multitude of different aspects of ontology development and usage, from the philosophical aspects to the practical usage case scenarios. Still, the large and proactive participation to this workshop (and to the other OntoCommons workshops) demonstrates the awareness of this community about the major role that the path towards digitalization undertaken by the EC may reserve to ontologies, especially to facilitate the **human-to-machine** and **machine-to-human** interactions. The **summary document** lists most of the relevant topics that the ontology community should address to step forward in the adoption of ontological approach to wider audiences, exploiting the untapped potential that ontologies provide when dealing with knowledge management.

7. Appendix

7.1 Survey Text

04/11/21, 23:33 Top Level and Mid Level Multi Disciplinary Ontology Workshop Questionnaire

Top Level and Mid Level Multi Disciplinary Ontology Workshop Questionnaire

The questionnaire is aimed to collect preliminary information that will help organizers to address the topic that will be discussed during the workshop and to prepare the final workshop report.

* Required

Definitions

A Top Level Ontology (TLO) provides a formal characterization of general concepts according to specific ontological perspectives, providing basic relations and conceptual framework for lower, more detailed, ontology modules.

Middle Level Ontologies (MLOs) extend TLO concepts towards a specific discipline (e.g. manufacturing, materials science, chemistry) with the aim to provide a core shared vocabulary for lower level modules. A MLO will provide a higher level of detail than a TLO, extending the taxonomical structure of the ontology more along on the horizontal dimension.

A Domain Level Ontology (DLO) targets a specific domain of applications (e.g. additive manufacturing, composite materials). A DLO is characterized by an increased level of detail with respect to an MLO, a more pronounced horizontal extension and a strong dependency on the domain of application, while still maintaining some neutrality with respect to the specific problem addressed.

An Application Level Ontology (ALO) is aimed to represent specific application cases (e.g. a device from a specific manufacturer) with highly specialized classes and individuals.

1. An ontology should always refer to a Top Level Ontology. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

2. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

3. A TLO greatly facilitates the development of ontologies in general. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

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1/6

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Top Level and Mid Level Multi Disciplinary Ontology Workshop Questionnaire

4. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

5. TLOs are difficult to understand since they refer to terms and concepts not clearly understandable by people working on the application fields. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

6. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

7. A clear philosophical commitment (e.g. realism, nominalism) is important for a TLO. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

8. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

9. There is not a single TLO which is valid for all purposes, since there are more ways to express general concepts depending on the ontologist perspective. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

10. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

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2/6

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Top Level and Mid Level Multi Disciplinary Ontology Workshop Questionnaire

11. I prefer to stick on the conceptualization/axiomatization developed ad hoc for my approach than changing my perspective adopting a more general TLO/MLO. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

12. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

13. Adoption of common TLO/MLO greatly enhances interoperability between ontologies. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

14. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

15. In the trade off between expressivity (e.g. FOL vs RDF) and tractability (e.g. undecidability vs decidability, computational efficiency) I prefer tractability. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

16. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

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3/6

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Top Level and Mid Level Multi Disciplinary Ontology Workshop Questionnaire

17. The ability to infer new statements from given knowledge is the most important feature for a TLO/MLO. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

18. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

19. A good documentation is paramount for the effective use of a TLO/MLO as a basis for DLO. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

20. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

21. A MLO should be defined according to the discipline of interest (e.g. chemistry) instead of according to its formal structure (e.g. taxonomy class levels) *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

22. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

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Top Level and Mid Level Multi Disciplinary Ontology Workshop Questionnaire

23. The choice of an ontology for my application is driven by the requirements/limitations of the tools I'm planning to use or that are available to me. *

Mark only one oval.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Total Disagreement	<input type="radio"/>	Total Agreement										

24. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

25. Quantify the relevance of each of the following ontology levels in practical applications: *

Mark only one oval per row.

	0 (not relevant)	1	2	3	4 (highly relevant)
Top Level Ontologies	<input type="radio"/>				
Mid Level Ontologies	<input type="radio"/>				
Domain Level Ontologies	<input type="radio"/>				
Application Level Ontologies	<input type="radio"/>				

26. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

27. There is lack of tools or need for further developments in order to enable or facilitate the TLO/MLO development and usage in practice *

Mark only one oval per row.

	0 (not relevant)	1	2	3	4 (highly relevant)
Editors	<input type="radio"/>				
Reasoners	<input type="radio"/>				
Provers	<input type="radio"/>				
Visualization	<input type="radio"/>				
Optimization	<input type="radio"/>				

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1wotNuoJX5-VKZoRAyiT3piU_TzEXAvZIEVNz-eNjB2g/edit

5/6

04/11/21, 23:33

Top Level and Mid Level Multi Disciplinary Ontology Workshop Questionnaire

28. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

29. Which language do you prefer for TLO/MLO development/usage: *

Mark only one oval.

- HOL
- FOL
- OWL
- RDFS
- Other: _____

30. Please motivate your answer to the previous question:

31. What are the bottlenecks or unresolved issues that are actually preventing or slowing the use of ontologies in Europe scientific and industrial landscape? *

32. What are the unexploited capabilities of ontologies that could contribute to the digitalisation of scientific and industrial sectors? *

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Google Forms

7.2 List of Participants

	Name	Surname	Country	Organisation	Professional role
1	Emanuele	Ghedini	Italy	University of Bologna	Ontologist
2	Maunya	Doroudi Moghadam	Norway	University of Oslo	
3	Robert	Rovetto	Italy	International Association for Ontology and its Applications	Ontologist
4	Gerhard	Goldbeck	United Kingdom	Goldbeck Consulting Ltd	Manager
5	Emilio	Sanfilippo	Italy	National Research Council (CNR)	Researcher
6	Roberto	Rosso	Italy	QED srl	Manager
7	Robert	Daniels-Dwyer	United Kingdom	HS2	
8	Riccardo	Baratella	Italy	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	Researcher
9	Anne-Francoise	Cutting-Decelle	France	University of Geneva / CUI	Researcher
10	Salvatore	Florio	United Kingdom	University of Birmingham	Researcher
11	Pance	Panov	Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	Scientist
12	Fahad	Khan	Italy	Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale "Antonio Zampolli"	Researcher
13	Ana	Kostovska	Slovenia	Jozef Stefan Institute	
14	Megan	Katsumi	Canada	University of Toronto	
15	Luan	Fonseca Garcia	Brazil	UFRGS	Ontologist
16	João Paulo	Almeida	Brazil	Federal University of Espirito Santo	Researcher
17	Sandy	Bei	Belgium	IRES	Scientist
18	Benjami	Moreno Torres	Germany	Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung	Researcher
19	Luis	Ramos	Germany	FHS Potsdam	Ontologist
20	Nicolau	Santos	Brazil	UFRGS	Researcher
21	Alcides	Gonçalves Lopes Junior	Brazil	Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul	Researcher
22	Ana	Correia	Germany	ATB-Bremen	Researcher
23	Mark	Ressler	United States of America	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Ontologist
24	John	Ambrosiano	United States of America	Los Alamos National Laboratory	Scientist
25	Dusan	Sormaz	United States of America	Ohio University	Researcher
26	Dimitris	Kiritsis	Switzerland	EPFL-UiO	Researcher
27	Dragan	Stokic	Germany	ATB- Bremen	Researcher
28	Ravi	Sharma	United States of America	R S Enterprises	Scientist
29	Ebrahim	Norouzi	Germany	Fraunhofer	Scientist
30	Francesca	Bleken	Norway	SINTEF	Researcher
31	Tiago	Prince Sales	Italy	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	Researcher
32	Allan	Mazimwe	Uganda	Makerere University	Researcher
33	Laure	Vieu	France	IRIT-CNRS	Researcher
34	Roberta	Ferrario	Italy	Institute of Cognitive Sciences and Technologies - CNR	Researcher
35	Claudio	Masolo	Italy	CNR	Researcher

36	Zubeida	Dawood	South Africa	CSIR	Researcher
37	Gabriela	Velea	Netherlands	Shell	Other (please specify)
38	Mariya	Evtimova	France	INRAE	Engineer
39	Claudenir	M. Fonseca	Italy	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	Ontologist
40	Chris	Partridge	United Kingdom	BORO Solutions	Ontologist
41	Riichiro	Mizoguchi	Japan	Japan Advanced Institute of Science and Technology	Researcher
42	Carlos	Kavka	Slovenia	ESTECO SpA	Researcher
43	Theodoros	Efthymiadis	Greece	IRES (Innovation in Research and Engineering Solutions)	
44	Nicola	Guarino	Italy	CNR	Researcher
45	Hedi	Karray	France	ENIT	Ontologist
46	Matthias	Büschelberger	Germany	Fraunhofer IWM	Ontologist
47	Joe	Gregory	United Kingdom	University of Bristol	Engineer
48	Casper	Andersen	Switzerland	EPFL	Researcher
49	Yoav	Nahshon	Germany	Fraunhofer IWM	Engineer
50	Joachim	Wackerow	Germany	GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences	
51	Sofia	Tsekeridou	Greece	INTRASOFT International S.A.	Manager
52	Anne	de Baas	Belgium	Consultant	Researcher
53	Michela	Magas	Sweden	Industry Commons Foundation	Manager
54	Stefano	Borgo	Italy	Laboratory for Applied Ontology ISTC-CNR	Researcher
55	Carmen	Chui	Canada	University of Toronto	Researcher
56	Jesper Friis	Friis	Norway	SINTEF	Scientist
57	Treesa	Joseph	Norway	SINTEF	Engineer
58	Themis	Anagnostopoulos	Greece	INTRASOFT-International	Engineer
59	Markus	Niebel	Germany	Fraunhofer IWM	
60	Zubeida	Dawood	South Africa	CSIR	Researcher
61	Michael	Hoffmann	Germany	Fraunhofer IFAM	Scientist
62	Alberto	Martinez	Belgium	Procter and Gamble	
63	Michael	Noeske	Germany	Fraunhofer IFAM	Researcher
64	Pierre	Grenon	United Kingdom	BORO Solutions	Ontologist
65	Ana	Costa	Italy	Università degli Studi di Firenze	Researcher
66	Martin G	Skjæveland	Norway	University of Oslo	Researcher
67	Matthew	West	United Kingdom	Information Junction Ltd	Engineer
68	Jens	Otten	Norway	University of Oslo	
69	Eduard	Kamburjan	Norway	University of Oslo	Researcher
70	Peter	McQuilton	United Kingdom	University of Oxford, UK	
71	Lucas	Vieira	Brazil	UFRGS	Researcher
72	Farhad	Ameri	United States of America	Texas State Univerisy	Researcher
73	Dag	Hovland	Norway	University of Oslo	Researcher
74	Petr	Křemen	Czech Republic	1) Czech Technical University in Prague, 2) Ministry of Interior of the Czech Republic	Ontologist
75	Paraskevas	Bourgos	Luxembourg	INTRASOFT INTERNATIONAL S.A.	
76	Ole Magnus	Holter	Norway	University of Oslo	Researcher

77	Amir Laadhar	Laadhar	Denmark	Aalborg University	Researcher
78	Pooyan	Ramezani Besheli	Belgium	Ghent University	Researcher
79	Joana	Morgado	Germany	Fraunhofer IWM	Researcher
80	Siraj	Rehman	United Kingdom	Atkins	Other
81	Carlos	Fonseca	Brazil	UFES	
82	Alexandra	Simperler	United Kingdom	Goldbeck Consulting	Other
83	Maria	Keet	South Africa	University of Capw Town	Scientist
84	Daniel	Bakkelund	Norway	University of Oslo	Researcher
85	Jairo	Souza	Brazil	Federal University of Juiz de Fora	Researcher
86	Aileen	Kennedy	Ireland	National University of Ireland GALway	
87	Huanyu	Li	Sweden	Linköping University	Ontologist
88	Antony	Galton	United Kingdom	University of Exeter (retired)	Researcher
89	Mike	Bennett	United Kingdom	Hypercube Ltd.	Ontologist
90	Jana	Ahmad	Czech Republic	Czech technical university in Prague	Researcher
91	César	Bernabé	Brazil	LUMC	
92	David	Price	United Kingdom	TopQuadrant	Ontologist
93	Øystein	Linnebo	Norway	University of Oslo	Researcher
94	Simon	Clark	Norway	SINTEF Industry	
95	Stevensymphony	Kraines	Japan	Symphony	
96	Nils	Van den Steen	Belgium	Vrije Universiteit Brussel	
97	Emilio	Sanfilippo	Italy	National Research Council (CNR)	Researcher
98	Willem	van Dorp	Netherlands	Uniresearch	Manager
99	Pierpaolo	Sichera	Italy	ISTC-CNR	Researcher
100	Dimitris	Kiritsis	Switzerland	EPFL-UiO	Researcher
101	Imran	KHAN	France	Schneider Electric Industries	Manager
102	Moritz	Blum	Germany	Bielefeld University	
103	Basil	Eil	Germany	Bielefeld University, Oslo University	Researcher
104	Jörg F.	Unger	Germany	BAM	Researcher
105	Ingo	Steinbach	Germany	Ruhr-Universität Bochum	Scientist
106	Ya-Fan	Chen	Germany	Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena	
107	Philipp	von Hartrott	Germany	Fraunhofer IWM	Scientist
108	Jaime	A. Pinto	Brazil	UFMG	Ontologist
109	Ana Marilza	Pernas	Brazil	UFPeI	Scientist
110	Jürgen	Olbricht	Germany	Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung (BAM)	Scientist
111	Bernd	Bayerlein	Germany	Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung (BAM)	Scientist
112	KATE	REVOREDO	Austria	Vienna University of Economics and Business	Researcher
113	mattia	falduti	Italy	unibz	
114	ravi	patel	Germany	kit	Researcher
115	Maria das Graças	da Silva Teixeira	Brazil	Federal University of Espírito Santo	Researcher / Professor

116	Rebecca	Siafaka	Greece	ATB	Engineer
117	Guylherme	Figueiredo	Brazil	Petrobras	Ontologist
118	Sebastiano	Moruzzi	Italy	Università degli Studi di Bologna	Ontologist
119	Alessandro	Mosca	Italy	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	Researcher
120	Sylvain	MARIE	France	Railenium	Engineer
121	Jussara Teixeira	Teixeira	Brazil	UFES	Researcher
122	Sana	Debbeck	France	IRT Railenium	Researcher
123	Heiko	Beinersdorf	Germany	MFPA	Researcher
124	Joao	Moreira	Netherlands	U.Twente	Researcher
125	Ahmed	Aslam	Germany	Max-Planck-Institut für Eisenforschung GmbH	
126	Henrik	Forssell	Norway	IFI, UIO	Researcher
127	Felix	Arendt	Germany	FSU Jena	Researcher
128	Illmayer	Klaus	Austria	Austrian Academy of Sciences: Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Heritage Science	Researcher
129	Modeus	Abdelnaby	Germany	UzL	Researcher
130	Pierre	Grenon	United Kingdom	BORO Solutions	Ontologist
131	Vogt	Lars	Germany	Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology University Library	Scientist
132	Mossakowski	Till	Germany	Otto-von-Guericke Universität Magdeburg	Scientist
133	Tatyana	Sheveleva	Germany	TIB – Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology and University Library	Researcher
134	Nikolaos	Nikoloudakis	Greece	National Technical University of Athens	Researcher
135	Martin Thomas	Horsch	Germany	Innovation Centre for Process Data Technology	Engineer
136	José Manuel	Domínguez	Germany	Fraunhofer IWM	
137	Silvia	Chiacchiera	United Kingdom	Science and Technology Facilities Council, UK Research and Innovation (STFC/UKRI)	Scientist
138	Jim	Logan	United States of America	Dassault Systemès	Ontologist
139	Thiago	Thomes Coelho	Brazil	NA	Researcher
140	Luca	Foschini	Italy	University of Bologna	Researcher
141	Ludger	Jansen	Germany	WWU	Researcher
142	Luigi	Asprino	Italy	University of Bologna	
143	Valentina	Presutti	Italy	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna	Researcher
144	Sergio	López López	Netherlands	Software for Chemistry & Materials (SCM)	Manager
145	Ludovica	Marinucci	Italy	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR)	Researcher
146	Markus	Stumptner	Australia	University of South Australia	Researcher
147	Fabrizio	Smith	Italy	COLLINS AEROSPACE	Engineer
148	Alexandru	Todor	Germany	Fraunhofer Materials	

149	Pablo	Lopez-Tarifa	Netherlands	eScience Center	Software Engineer
150	Daniela	Schmidt	Brazil	UFRGS	Researcher
151	Isa	Salgado	Brazil	Universidade de Brasília	Researcher
152	raza	naqi	Pakistan	Superior	Ontologist
153	Fabian	Neuhaus	Germany	Otto von Guericke University	Scientist
154	Frank	Loebe	Germany	University of Leipzig	Ontologist
155	Arkopaul	Sarkar	United States of America	ENIT	Researcher
156	Tatjana	Krups	Germany	Deutsches Institut für Kautschuktechnologie e.V	researcher
157	Dario	Campagna	Italy	ESTECO SPA	Senior Researcher
158	Núria	Queralt Rosinach	Spain	Leiden University Medical Centre	
159	Laura Slaughter	Slaughter	Norway	UiO	Researcher
160	Elena	Garcia Trelles	Germany	Fraunhofer IWM	Engineer
161	Patryk	Burek	Poland	UMCS	
162	David	Linke	Germany	Leibniz-Institut für Katalyse	Researcher
163	Margherita	Porena	Italy	CNR-ISTC	Researcher
164	Atul	Agrawal	Germany	Technical University of Munich	
165	Alba	Fernández-Izquierdo	Spain	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Ontologist
166	Lorenzo	Solano	Spain	Universitat Politècnica de València	Other
167	Lorenzo	Solano	Spain	Universitat Politècnica de València	Other
168	Rita	Giuffrida	Italy	Trust-IT Services	Research analyst
170	José	Palazzo Moreira de Oliveira	Brazil	Federal University of RS	Researcher
171	Ulrike	Parson	Germany	parson AG	Other
172	Miroslav	Blasko	Czech Republic	Czech Technical University in Prague	Engineer
173	Lucas	Vieira	Brazil	UFRGS	Researcher
174	Marek	Sierka	Germany	Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena	
175	Lucas	Vieira	Brazil	UFRGS	Researcher
176	Fabício Henrique	Rodrigues	Brazil	Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS)	Researcher
177	Zola	Mahlaza	South Africa	University of Cape Town	
178	Tezira	Wanyana	South Africa	University of Cape Town	Researcher
179	Frances	Gillis-Webber	South Africa	University of Cape Town	Other
180	Toky Hajatiana	RABOANARY	South Africa	University of Cape Town	Researcher
181	Adrien	Barton	France	IRIT, CNRS	Researcher
182	Maria	Kostopoulou	Greece	ElvalHalcor	Project Administrator and reporting analyst

183	Selenia	Anastasi	Italy	Università di Catania	
184	Tony	Huang	Canada	City of Toronto	Engineer
185	Sascha	Fliegener	Germany	Fraunhofer-Institut für Werkstoffmechanik (IWM)	
186	Giorgio	La Civita	Italy	University Of Bologna	Researcher
187	Bruno Lopes Machado	Lopes Machado	Brazil	TATA Counsultancy Services	
188	Helm	Dirk	Germany	Fraunhofer Institute for Mechanics of Materials IWM	Scientist
189	Andrey	Vukolov	Italy	ELETTRA Sincrotrone Trieste	Researcher
190	Blask	Oliver	Germany	Karlsruher Institute for Technology	Scientist
191	Admin	IMB	Germany	KIT	
192	Selenia	Anastasi	Italy	Università di Catania	
193	Andrew	Mitchell	United Kingdom	BORO Solutions	Ontologist
194	Arild	Waalert	Norway	University of Oslo	Researcher
195	Núria	Queralt Rosinach	Spain	Leiden University Medical Centre	
196	Pierluigi	Del Nostro	Italy	Goldbeck Consulting	
197	Walter	Carnielli	Italy	Laboratory for Applied Ontology (LOA) , Trento, Italy	Researcher
198	Jayendra	Ganguli	United States of America	Raytheon	Manager
199	Selenia	Anastasi	Italy	Università di Catania	
200	Jan Emil	Larsen	Denmark	LIT.dk	Researcher
201	adham	Hashibon	Germany	Materially - The Materials Development Marketplace GmbH	Manager
202	Amit	Bhave	United Kingdom	CMCL Innovations	
203	George	Brownbridge	United Kingdom	CMCL Innovations	Software developer
204	Daniel Nurkowski	Nurkowski	United Kingdom	CMCL Innovations	Scientist
205	Leyla	Garcia	Germany	ZB MED	Researcher
206	Núria	Queralt Rosinach	Spain	Leiden University Medical Centre	
207	Dmitry	Baranov	Latvia	CTCo	Architect